

Synthesis of 2-Aryl-2,3-dihydro-oxazolo[3,2 : 1,2]pyrrolo[3,4 : 3,2]pyridin-5-one and 2-Aryl-2,3-dihydro-oxazolo[3,2 : 1,2]-pyrrolo[3,4 : 2,3]pyridin-5-one

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A variety of 2-aryl-2,3-dihydro-oxazolo[3,2 : 1,2]pyrrolo[3,4 : 3,2]pyridin-5-one and 2-aryl-2,3-dihydro-oxazolo[3,2 : 1,2]pyrrolo[3,4 : 2,3]pyridin-5-one were prepared. The absolute configuration of the chiral centers were studied thoroughly from which the structural and stereoformulae of these compounds were deduced by using nmr and microanalysis technique.

It is known that some oxazolo[2,3 : *a*]isoindol-5-(9*b* *H*)-one derivatives (I) have pharmaceutical effects¹. In this project we intend to synthesise a similar structure to I but containing pyridine ring rather than benzene ring in the fused system which is oxazolo[3',2' : 1,2]pyrrolo[3,4 : 3,2]pyridin-5-one (II).

To achieve this objective, a variety of 1-aryl-2-aminoethanols, ethyl 3-formylpicolinate and ethyl 2-formylnicotinate were prepared, followed by condensation reactions of these compounds to synthesise the target compounds.

Results and Discussion

The synthesis of ethyl 3-formylpicolinate (6) was accomplished through a linear synthesis by oxidising 8-hydroxyquinoline (1) by nitric acid² to get a mixture of compounds 2 and 3 which were separated by crystallisation from water followed by treatment of 2 with sodium metabisulphite and concentrated HCl to get the hydrochloride (4) which gave a mixture of compounds 5 and 6 in its treatment with ethanol in the presence of concentrated H₂SO₄. Compound 8 was obtained by preparing the ester (7) from the acid (3) by treating it with ethanol and concentrated H₂SO₄ and reducing this ester with DIBAH³ (Scheme 1).

When equivalent amounts of the ethanolamine (10) and ethyl 3-formylpicolinate (6) or ethyl 2-formylnicotinate (8) were refluxed in benzene, two

diastereoisomeric compounds of (2*SR*, 9*b* *SR*)-2-aryl-2,3-dihydro-oxazolo[3,2 : 1,2]pyrrolo[3,4 : 3,2]pyridin-5-one (11) and (2*SR*, 9*b* *RS*)-2-aryl-2,3-dihydro-oxazolo[3,2 : 1,2]pyrrolo[3,4 : 3,2]pyridin-

5-one (**12**) were isolated and separated from the reaction of **10** with **6**; and two diastereoisomeric compounds of (2*RS*, 9*b RS*)-2-aryl-2,3-dihydro-oxazolo[3,2 : 1,2]pyrrolo[3,4 : 2,3]pyridin-5-one (**13**) and (2*RS*, 9*b SR*)-2-aryl-2,3-dihydro-oxazolo[3,2 : 1,2]pyrrolo[3,4 : 2,3]pyridin-5-one (**14**) were isolated and separated from the reaction of **10** with **8** (Scheme 2).

Ar = phenyl (a), β -naphthyl (b), *p*-chlorophenyl (c), 3,4-dimethoxyphenyl (d), 3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl (e)

Scheme 2

Presumably, the mechanism of the reaction begins with formation of the Schiff base (**15**) and its enantiomer, followed by nucleophilic attack of oxygen on the imine carbon below or above the plane of C=N gives the oxazolidines **16** and **17** and then cyclisation with the loss of one molecule of ethanol leads to the final products **11** and **12** and their enantiomers (Scheme 3). This mechanism was supported by the fact that the reaction of the aldehyde-ester (**6**) with the amine (**10a**) in benzene at room temperature gave the Schiff base (**18**) as a major product, and the two isomers (**11a**) and (**12a**) in very low yield.

The stereochemistry and structures of the diastereomeric compounds obtained in Scheme 2 and structures of the compounds obtained in Scheme 1

were deduced and confirmed from their spectral data and elemental analyses. The most significant points in this regard are the ^1H nmr of the diastereoisomers (**11**, **12**) and (**13**, **14**) particularly the $\text{OCH}_A\text{CH}_B\text{H}_X\text{N}$ parts, which appear in compounds **11a-e** and **13a-e** as typical ABX system at δ 3.3, 4.6 and 5.1 for H_X , H_B and H_A respectively, with $J_{AB} \approx 6$ Hz, $J_{AX} \approx 8.5$ Hz and $J_{BX} \approx 12$ Hz and H_1 appears as a singlet at $\delta \approx 6.2$, whereas in compounds **12a-e** and **14a-e**, H_A appears as a triplet at $\delta \approx 5.5$ with $J \approx 7.5$ Hz and H_B , H_X appear as one doublet at $\delta \approx 3.9$ with $J \approx 7.5$ Hz, and H_1 appears as a singlet at $\delta \approx 6$. These differences of the chemical shifts between (**11**, **13**) and (**12**, **14**) can be attributed to the fact that H_1 in (**11**, **13**) is deshielded by its lying in the plane of the phenyl ring, whereas it is not so in compounds (**12**, **14**). H_A in compounds (**11**, **13**) is further shielded by ≈ 0.35 ppm; this may be attributed to its position nearer to the pyridine ring rather than in compounds (**12**, **14**).

Scheme 3

Proton H_B is very heavily deshielded in compounds (**11**, **13**) due to its position nearer to the plane of the carbonyl group than in compounds (**12**, **14**). The

carbonyl group effects similarly on H_X which comes nearer to its plane in compounds (**12**, **14**) rather than in compound (**11**, **13**). The above assignments were confirmed by obtaining the N.O.E. spectra for compounds **11a** and **12a**. The spectra of the two isomers were irradiated at the singlet of H_1 . This gave positive signals at δ 8.04 (H_9), 7.41 (ph) and 3.41 (H_X) in case of isomer **11a** and at δ 8.02 (H_9), 5.52 (H_A) in case of isomer **12a**. These 1H nmr spectra were found very similar to those obtained at 90 MHz with only one exception, that the signal due to H_B and H_X in compound **12a** appears as doublet at 90 MHz and quintet at 360 MHz due to the high resolution of the latter machine.

Experimental

1-Aryl-2-aminoethanols (10a-e) : β -Naphthylcyanohydrine (12.4 g, 0.068 mol) in dry tetrahydrofuran (80 ml) [ether in case of compounds **10c**, **10e**] was added dropwise to a slurry of lithium aluminium hydride (8.7 g) in dry tetrahydrofuran (320 ml), the reaction mixture being cooled at 0° . It was kept stirred at 0° for 6 h and at room temperature overnight, and then refluxed for 4 h. The complex was decomposed by water (8 ml), aqueous NaOH (20%, 15 ml) and water (8 ml) again. The resulting product was refluxed for 30 min, filtered hot, washed with hot tetrahydrofuran and the filtrate was dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate. The tetrahydrofuran was evaporated to yield 1-(β -naphthyl)-2-aminoethanol (**10b**) as yellowish solid which was pure enough to be used in the condensation (12 g, 94.7%), m.p. $91-93^\circ$; 1H nmr δ ($CDCl_3$ with drops of $DMSO-d_6$) 2.7 (3H, br, OH, NH_2 exchanged with D_2O), 2.9 (2H, d, J 6.2 Hz, CH_2), 4.5 (1H, t, J 6.2 Hz, CH) and 7.72-7.75 (7H, m, ArH).

Similar procedure⁴ was adopted to prepare the following 1-aryl-2-aminoethanols from the corresponding cyanohydrine. In case of compounds **10a** and **10d** the crude products were purified by dissolving in ethanol and passing dry hydrogen chloride gas into the solution till saturation. Ethanol was then evaporated to give the amine hydrochloride, which was converted to amine by adding KOH pellets to aqueous solution of the amine hydrochloride until strongly alkaline (pH about 12), and then extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate. Chloroform was then evaporated to give the pure

amine. Compounds **10c** and **10e** were purified by dissolving in chloroform and extracting with aqueous HCl (1M). The aqueous layer was made alkaline with KOH pellets and extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was then dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate and the solvent evaporated : 1-phenyl-2-aminoethanol (**10a**; 64%), m.p. $41-42^\circ$ (lit.⁵ $40-41^\circ$); 1H nmr δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.8 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, CH_2), 3.0-3.1 (3H, br, OH, NH_2), 4.6 (5H, m, ArH), 5.4 (1H, t, J 6 Hz, CH) and 7.3-7.5 (5H, m, ArH); 1-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-2-aminoethanol (**10c**; 80%), m.p. $85-87^\circ$ (lit.⁵ $90-92^\circ$); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.26 (3H, br, OH, NH_2), 2.75 (2H, m, CH_2), 4.55 (1H, m, CH) and 7.16-7.4 (4H, m, ArH); 1-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-2-aminoethanol (**10d**; 40.9%), m.p. $76-78^\circ$ (lit.⁶ 77°); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.6 (3H, br, OH, NH_2), 2.8 (2H, m, CH_2), 3.8 (6H, s, $2CH_3O$), 4.51 (1H, t, J 6 Hz, CH) and 6.75-6.9 (3H, m, ArH); 1-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-aminoethanol (**10e**; 76%), m.p. $71-73^\circ$ (lit.⁵ $72-74^\circ$); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.06 (3H, br, OH, NH_2 , exchanged with D_2O), 2.8 (2H, m, CH_2), 4.5 (1H, m, CH), 5.9 (2H, s, OCH_2O) and 6.75-6.81 (3H, m, ArH).

Pyridine-2,3-dicarboxylic acid (3) and 2-carboxy-3-pyridineglyoxylic acid (2) : 8-Hydroxyquinoline (150 g) was added in small portions to concentrated HNO_3 (1 dm³) with stirring and cooled to $0-5^\circ$. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature overnight and then refluxed for 1 h. The solution was divided into 100 ml portions, and every portion was treated separately in the following ways.

It was evaporated to dryness and the residue was treated with water (50 ml) to yield pyridine-2,3-dicarboxylic acid (**3**; 90 g, 52.3%), m.p. $230-32^\circ$ (m.m.p. with commercial sample $231-232^\circ$) (lit.⁷ 229°); 1H nmr δ ($DMSO-d_6$) 7.6 (1H, dd, J 6, 8 Hz, H-5), 8.22 (1H, dd, J 8, 2 Hz, H-4), 8.69 (1H, dd, J 6, 2 Hz, H-6) and 12.7 (2H, br, $2CO_2H$, exchanged with D_2O); m/z 123 (M^+-CO_2 , 100) 105 (50) and 77 (40.7). The filtrate was evaporated to dryness, the residue treated with water (25 ml) and stirred overnight to crystallise 2-carboxy-3-pyridineglyoxylic acid (**2**; 48 g, 23.8%), m.p. $168-70^\circ$ (lit.² $174-76^\circ$); δ ($DMSO-d_6$) 7.75 (1H, dd, J 6, 8 Hz, H-5), 8.1 (1H, dd, J 8, 2 Hz, H-4), 8.9 (1H, dd, J 6, 2 Hz, H-6) and 11.2 (2H, br, $2CO_2H$, exchanged with D_2O); m/z 150 (M^+-CO_2H , 27.8), 123 (100), 105 (59.2) and 77 (59).

3-Formylpicolinic acid hydrochloride (4) : A mixture of 2-carboxy-3-pyridineglyoxylic acid (5 g) and sodium metabisulphite (7 g) was stirred in water (50 ml) at room temperature for 4 h and the solution was evaporated to dryness. The residue was shaken vigorously with concentrated HCl. This caused a precipitation of sodium chloride which was filtered off. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness. The HCl treatment was repeated twice to give a hygroscopic material which was identified as 3-formylpicolinic acid hydrochloride (4); ^1H nmr δ (DMSO- d_6) 7.79 (1H, dd, J 8, 6 Hz, H-5), 8.21 (1H, dd, J 8, 2 Hz, H-4), 8.92 (1H, dd, J 6, 2 Hz, H-6) and 9.52 (1H, s, CO_2H).

An attempt to prepare 3-formylpicolinic acid, according to the reported procedure², failed, giving an unidentified product.

Reaction of 3-formylpicolinic acid hydrochloride (4) with ethanol : A mixture of 3-formylpicolinic acid hydrochloride (22 g), excess of ethanol (50 ml) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (10 g) was refluxed in dry benzene (170 ml) for 16 h provided with Dean and Stark trap. During this time some water collected from the reaction. Benzene and excess of ethanol were then evaporated, the residue was treated with saturated solution of NaHCO_3 and extracted with chloroform three times. Chloroform on evaporation gave an oily product which was submitted to a silica gel column chromatography and eluted with ethyl acetate in petroleum ether (5–50%). The separation gave ethyl-3-(diethoxymethyl)picolinate (5; 4 g, 20%) as viscous liquid (Found : C, 61.9; H, 7.55; N, 5.31. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_4$ requires : C, 61.64; H, 7.56; N, 5.53); ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 1.2 (6H, t, J 6 Hz, 2CH_3), 3.2 (3H, t, J 8 Hz, ester CH_3), 3.6 (4H, m, 2CH_2), 4.42 (2H, q, J 8 Hz, ester CH_2), 6.09 (1H, s, O-CH-O), 7.41 (1H, dd, J 6, 8 Hz, H-5), 8.1 (1H, dd, J 8, 2 Hz, H-4) and 8.6 (1H, dd, J 6, 2 Hz, H-6); m/z 224 ($M^+ - \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, 40), 208 (52), 180 (50), 150 (63), 134 (100), 106 (53), 78 (27) and 47 (19); ν_{max} (CHCl_3) 3 300, 1 730, 1 590, 1 440, 1 370, 1 300 and 1 060 cm^{-1} ; and ethyl 3-formylpicolinate (6; 18 g, 80%) as an oil (Found : C, 60.52; H, 5.45; N, 7.78. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{NO}_3$ requires : C, 60.33; H, 5.08; N, 7.82); ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 1.45 (3H, t, J 8 Hz, CH_3), 4.54 (2H, q, J 8 Hz, CH_2), 7.65 (1H, dd, J 6, 8 Hz, H-5), 8.28 (1H, dd, J 8, 2 Hz, H-4), 8.89 (1H, dd, J 6, 2 Hz, H-6) and 10.6 (1H, s, CHO); m/z 150 ($M^+ - \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, 9), 134

(14), 106 (41), 78 (100) and 51 (17); ν_{max} (CDCl_3) 3 300, 1 715, 1 580, 1 440, 1 370, 1 300, 1 130 and 1 080 cm^{-1} .

Reaction of pyridine-2,3-dicarboxylic acid (3) with ethanol : A mixture of pyridine-2,3-dicarboxylic acid (30 g), excess of ethanol (60 ml) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (12 g) was refluxed in dry benzene (200 ml) for 16 h provided with Dean and Stark trap. The solvent and excess ethanol was then evaporated to dryness and the residue neutralised with saturated solution of NaHCO_3 and extracted with chloroform. The extract was dried with anhydrous magnesium sulphate and chloroform was evaporated to leave ethyl pyridine-2,3-dicarboxylate (7; 32.7 g, 70%) as an oil; ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 1.4 (6H, m, 2CH_3), 4.4 (4H, quintet, 2CH_2), 7.4 (1H, dd, J 6, 8 Hz, H-5), 8.19 (1H, dd, J 8, 2 Hz, H-4) and 8.72 (1H, dd, J 6, 2 Hz, H-6).

Reduction of ethyl pyridine-2,3-dicarboxylate (7) with diisobutyl aluminumhydride : In a very dry condition and under nitrogen, a solution of ethylpyridine-2,3-dicarboxylate (7; 30 g) in dry toluene (673 ml) was refrigerated at -70° . Diisobutyl aluminum hydride (20% in hexane; 200 ml) was then added to the above solution over a period of 2 h, during which time the ester (7) disappeared completely. The mixture was stirred for 20 min, then a mixture of acetic acid (34 ml), water (8 ml) and ether (67 ml) was added over a period of 30 min. The temperature was raised to 10° over a period of 30 min. The resulting solid was washed with hot toluene (2×134 ml). The filtrate and the combined extract were evaporated to dryness to give an oily product which was dissolved in water (27 ml) and neutralised with saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate, then extracted with chloroform. The extract was dried with anhydrous magnesium sulphate to give an oily product (13 g) which was chromatographed on a silica gel column and eluted with ethyl acetate in petroleum ether (5–50%). It gave ethyl-2-formyl nicotinate (8; 9 g, 37.5%) as oil (Found : C, 60.47; H, 4.9; N, 8.0. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{NO}_3$ requires : C, 60.33; H, 5.03; N, 7.82); ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 1.4 (3H, t, J 8 Hz, CH_3), 4.5 (2H, q, J 8 Hz, CH_2), 7.6 (1H, dd, J 6, 8 Hz, H-5), 8.2 (1H, dd, J 8, 2 Hz, H-4), 8.9 (1H, dd, J 6, 2 Hz, H-6) and 10.4 (1H, s, CHO); m/z 150 ($M^+ - \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, 11), 134 (13), 106 (43) and 78 (100); ν_{max} (CDCl_3) 3 060, 2 940, 2 886, 2 841, 1 745, 1 588, 1 460, 1 300,

1 150 and 1 080 cm^{-1} ; and 2,3-pyridine dicarboxaldehyde (**9**; 3 g, 16.5%) as an oil, ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 7.67 (1H, dd, J 6, 8 Hz, H-5), 8.4 (1H, dd, J 8, 2 Hz, H-4), 9.0 (1H, dd, J 6, 2 Hz, H-6), 10.15 (1H, s, CHO) and 10.76 (1H, s, CHO).

Condensation of 1-aryl-2-aminoethanol (10 and 12–15) with ethyl 3-formylpicolinate (6) and with ethyl 2-formyl nicotinate (8): Ethyl 3-formylpicolinate (**6**) and equivalent amount of 1-aryl-2-aminoethanols (**10a–e**) were mixed in benzene (40 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 6 h provided with Dean and Stark trap. Benzene was then evaporated to leave an oily product which was put on a silica gel column and eluted with ethyl acetate in petroleum ether (5–80%). This gave unreacted ethyl-3-formylpicolinate (0.3 g \pm 0.1 g) and (2*SR*, 9*bSR*)-2-aryl-2,3-dihydro-oxazolo[3',2' : 1,2]pyrrolo[3,4 : 3,2]pyridin-5-ones (**11a–e**; 24–36%) : **11a**, m.p. 136–38°, m/z 146 (100, M^+ –106), 118 (70.3), 105 (5), 91 (40.5), 77 (13.9), 64 (15.9) and 51 (12.3); CMR δ (CDCl_3) 170.7s, 152.9d, 151s, 138.5s, 138.1s, 132.45d, 128.8d, 128.6d, 126.5d, 126.05d, 89.1d, 82.7d and 50.7t; and (2*SR*, 9*bRS*)-2-aryl-2,3-dihydro-oxazolo[3',2' : 1,2]pyrrolo[3,4 : 3,2]pyridin-5-ones (**12a–e**; 14–23%) : **12a**, m.p. 102–04°, m/z 146 (100, M^+ –106), 118 (56.3), 105 (3.6), 91 (31.8), 77 (11), 64 (13.8) and 51 (10.6); CMR δ (CDCl_3) 170.7s, 153.1d, 151.75s, 138s, 136.4s, 132.6d, 128.75d, 128.7d, 126.2d, 126.1d, 89.3d, 84.9d and 49.8t.

This procedure was carried out to react ethyl 2-formyl nicotinate (**8**) with 1-aryl-2-aminoethanol (**10a–e**) to give (2*RS*, 9*bRS*)-2-aryl-2,3-dihydro-oxazolo[3',2' : 1,2]pyrrolo[3,4 : 2,3]pyridin-5-ones (**13a–e**; 9–34%) and (2*RS*, 9*bSR*)-2-aryl-2,3-dihydro-oxazolo[3',2' : 1,2]pyrrolo[3,4 : 2,3]pyridin-5-ones (**14a–e**; 3–16%) : **13a**, m.p. 97–99°; **b**, 174–75°; **c**, 167°; **d**, 156–57°; **e**, 193–94°; **14a**, m.p. 66–68°; **b**, 141–42°; **c**, 133°; **d**, oily; **e**, 144–45°. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

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References

1. W. J. HOULIHAN, *Chem Abstr.*, 1968, **68**, 5900.
2. F. BOTTARI and S. CARBONI, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1956, **86**, 990.
3. G. QUEFUINER and P. PASTOUR, *Bull. Soc. Fr.*, 1969, **10**, 3678.
4. N. ADITYA CHAUDHURY and A. CHATTERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 585
5. G. POOS, J. CARSON, J. R. KOWSKIE, N. KELLEY and J. MCGOWIN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1963, **6**, 266.
6. K. KINDLER and W. PESCHKE, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1931, **269**, 581.
7. S. HOOGWERFF and W. A. DROP, *Chem Bar.*, 1979, **12**, 747.

